

OpenSemanticWorld Introduction

Beschreibung

Keine Beschreibung vorhanden

[Als Präsentation anzeigen](#)

Background

OSWdb485a954a88465287b341d2897a84d6

Machine compatible name	OswIntroduction
Aussagen (ausgehend)	
Aussagen (eingehend)	
Es wurden keine Ergebnisse gefunden.	

Item

Type(s)/Category(s)	<i>Tutorial</i>
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Article

Tutorial

Prerequisites (required)

Prerequisites (optional)

Follow-up (recommended)

[Transcend wikitext to store and edit structured & linked data](#)
[OSW Python Package](#)
[OSW Ontology Import](#)

from: <https://kiprobatt.de>

Motivation

[Bearbeiten](#)

- Linked Data, Ontologies
- Shared Flexible and fast adaptable Data schemas
- Visual and programmatical interface

OpenSemanticWorld Concept

- No hardcoded schema, but set of predefined
- Build your own schema
 - Properties you need
 - Semantic context (optional)
 - Rendering (optional)
- Share via github / opensemantic.world

Technology Stack

Link to Ontologies

- Ontology classes are just specific schemas / schemas represent "icons" of "real objects"
- Automatic import via python (see: [Python Examples](#))
- Combination with data schemas, e. g. to populate autocomplete fields
- *Not just a static documentation*: Planned community interaction features
 - Comments => Github Issues,
 - Edits => Re-export => Github Pull request

Usecases and Applications

- Ontologies Documentation, Visualization, Demonstration (s. a. [Onto-Wiki](#))
- Tool and Workflow Registry ([Early Demo](#))
- Dataspace Catalogue
- LIMS, ELN ([Demo](#))
- ... whatever you want it to be

Tutorial Graph

- HasPart
- HasRequiredPredecessor
- HasOptionalPredecessor
- HasRecommendedSuccessor
- HasImage

Graph

- Reset view
- Copy permalink
- Save changes

Edit

- IsA
- HasSchema
- IsLocatedIn
- IsInstanceOf

Anhang

KiprobattKnowledgeGr
aphPng

 Dateien auswählen oder hierher ziehen...

jsondata